

D7.4: Interim report on communications

[WP7 – Communication and dissemination]

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Abstract

To achieve impact, SIENNA (Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact) needs to produce outputs that are relevant to stakeholders, timely and/or gives input to related processes. In essence, the ethical frameworks, codes of responsible conduct, recommendations for better legislation, methodologies for ethical and legal analysis, guidance for how to develop codes and guidelines, and methodology to reconcile the views of citizens and scientists must be relevant for, and desired by, the stakeholders they are designed for. This report shows the first steps taken to achieve this, and how collaboration with actors outside the project can create synergies that amplify the project's impact. We specifically outline SIENNA's impact strategy for artificial intelligence, which will help communicate, disseminate and exploit the SIENNA outputs and on which robotics, human genomics and human enhancement will build.

This document also reports on the scientific dissemination, external- and internal communication activities in the SIENNA project from October 2017 to May 2019. Data on website traffic and social media metrics is presented in six-month intervals to allow benchmarking. Further, this document establishes key performance indicators for web, social media and newsletters. The data in this document will form the basis for evaluating activities and developing strategy for how to use SIENNA channels in the future.

Document history

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Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
T7.1 Communication and dissemination plan	The social media strategy and outline for impact collaboration with the PANELFIT and SHERPA projects for AI & robotics is described in this document.

Linked task	Points of relevance
T7.2 Website launch and maintenance	The structural changes on the SIENNA website are described in this document.
T7.3 Graphical identity and guidelines for use	The visual identity for collaboration with the PANELFIT and SHERPA projects is outlined in this document.
T7.4 Scientific dissemination	This document lists key performance indicators (KPI's) for scientific dissemination as described in the description of action (DoA).
T7.5 Stakeholder communication and public relations	Stakeholder communication and public relations activities are reported in this document.
T7.6 Measuring outreach	Reports on dissemination and communication activities are annexed to this report, and KPI's listed in the document.
T1.4 Conduct stakeholder analysis and compile a contact list	The use of the stakeholder analysis contact list for e-mail newsletters and invitations to SIENNA events are described in this document.
T6.6 Formulate a sustainability plan	Input from this report will feed the exploitation and sustainability planning for SIENNA

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Executive summary

The SIENNA project has a diverse set of stakeholders in different technology domains that require tailored approaches to ensure we reach stakeholders with information that is of interest to them. SIENNA separates communications for human genomics, human enhancement, artificial intelligence (AI) & robotics in a number of ways: The website has separate landing pages per technology domain, we issue three separate newsletters and use different hashtags to reach stakeholder audiences on Twitter.

The three domains also offer different opportunities to collaborate with other initiatives, and there is more demand for the project's outputs in some areas. Currently, there are a number of opportunities in artificial intelligence given its policy significance, and this document describes the first steps to develop collaborations and synergies with other initiatives to achieve impact in this area. SIENNA already has an established collaboration with the PANELFIT (Participatory Approaches to a New Ethical and Legal Framework for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and SHERPA (Shaping the Ethical Dimensions of Smart Information Systems: a European Perspective) projects, with a number of communication and dissemination activities both accomplished and planned, and planning for collaboration with the Human Brain Project's (HBP) Ethics and Society sub project is underway. In connection with this impact strategy planning, the discussion on how to curate and sustain SIENNA outputs has been initiated, and work will continue in collaboration between WP6 and WP7 to align sustainability and exploitation planning with dissemination and communication plans to design impact strategy.

This report shows how dissemination and communication can help support impact by making SIENNA outputs **discoverable and findable** (using digital object identifiers (DOI) + complementary strategy to generate publicity); making our outputs **available** (using Open Access); making our outputs **relevant** (by re-framing and re-packaging content for different stakeholders and audiences); making what we do **understandable** (by translating content to other languages, and adapting the communication for different audiences). This report shows how we use the web, newsletters and social media (i.e., Twitter and YouTube) to amplify SIENNA messages, and how we measure outreach. The report presents key performance indicators (KPI's) for web, Twitter, YouTube (video watch time), and newsletters and offers interpretation and suggestions for how to use SIENNA channels in the future.

To ensure communications coming from the SIENNA project are relevant to stakeholders and other audiences, we separate the three domains in our communications. The website has four landing pages, one for the project as a whole (www.sienna-project.eu), one for human genomics (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/genomics/>), one for human enhancement (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/enhancement/>), and one for AI & robotics (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/robotics/>). The domain specific landing pages have mirrored structure, but tailored content. This will help ensure that visitors recognise the project, and find content that is *domain specific and relevant to them*. This strategy to separate communications is also mirrored in the stakeholder analysis and stakeholder contact list (developed in **T1.4**) and then applied to the newsletters, sending three separate mailings, with mirrored structures, and content tailored to the technology domain. In social media, this tactic is applied by using domain-specific hashtags (Twitter) and developing domain specific content (YouTube).

Data from the SIENNA website coupled with information on activities in other channels (Tweets, mailings etcetera) illustrates how we drive traffic between channels, and how web news items, static website content, video content, Tweets, events and e-mail communications are complementary and work together to promote the project and its outputs.

Next steps: The consortium is taking steps to identify the users of our frameworks, codes, recommendations, methodologies and guidance. Based on the outcomes of that work, and evaluation of the KPI's presented in this report, WP7 will continue to tailor the dissemination and communication strategy, developing tools and tactics to reach more specific stakeholder audiences to achieve the objectives of uptake and implementation. This will include presenting results at conferences, academic publications (DOI), editorial text, infographics & training, newsletters, media, social media, policy briefs and SIENNA workshops and other stakeholder interactions.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAAS	American Association for the Advancement of Science
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIHLEG	European Commission’s High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
DiVA	Digital Scientific Archive (in Swedish: Digitala Vetenskapliga Arkivet)
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ELSI	Ethical Legal and Social Issues
EMP	Ethical Monitoring Protocol
ESHG	European Society of Human Genomics
EU	European Union
FET	Future and Emerging Technologies)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
HBP	FET Flagship Human Brain Project
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
PANELFIT	Participatory Approaches to a New Ethical and Legal Framework for ICT (H2020 project)
PMC	Project Management Committee
SC42	Subcommittee 42 (in reference to International Organisation for Standardization)
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SHERPA	Shaping the ethical dimensions of Smart Information Systems (SIS) – A European Perspective (H2020 project)
SIENNA	Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
N/A	Not applicable
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
TBD	To be determined
UFRJ	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro
UPV	Unique Page Views
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UT	University of Twente
WP	Work Package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Audience	Group for which SIENNA communication or dissemination is targeted.
Bounce rate	A website's bounce rates is a representation of the percentage of website visitors who enter the site and then leave, or "bounce", rather than continuing to browse the website and view other pages on the same site.
Cookies	A small piece of data sent from a website and stored on the user's computer by the user's web browser while the user is browsing. Enabling tracking of user activity on the website, faster loading, saved logins, etc.
Consortium	Collectively, all parties that have signed the Consortium Agreement.
Consortium member	Individual involved in the SIENNA project.
Content owner	Individual responsible for accuracy of content in specified channel (or part of channel).
Data Protection Notice	Notice listing data controllers, the purposes and legal basis for processing personal data, the recipients of this personal data, the period and nature of processing, and the rights of the individual.
Dissemination	Active and tailored scientific (or research) communication of results to different academic audiences.
External communication	Adapting and informing about key messages and/or disseminations for different audiences.
FET Flagship	The FET Flagships are EU projects that are long term (10 year, 1 billion Euro), visionary, science-driven, large-scale research initiatives addressing grand scientific and technological challenges. Bringing together excellent research teams across various disciplines, sharing a unifying goal and an ambitious research roadmap on how to achieve it.
Impact collaboration	Process to co-create and amplify local impact. For the purposes of this report, the term is used to describe an approach engaging stakeholder audiences, developing key-messages together, and activating and leveraging existing networks and channels owned by audiences.
InfoGlue	Content Management System (CMS) used by Uppsala University.
Impressions	On Twitter, "Impressions" indicates the number of times a tweet has appeared in users' flows. On YouTube, "Impressions" indicates the number of times a "thumbnail" (i.e. the still image of the video) was shown to YouTube users.
Internal communication	Sharing information between partners and/or members within the SIENNA consortium
Key message	The main points SIENNA wants target audiences to hear and remember.
Landing page	Main point of entry (start page) for general and/or specific audiences on the SIENNA website.
Long-form content	In this report, long-form content is web text content that surpasses 700 words.
Organic reach	Social Media metric showing how many unique accounts have seen a post one time.

Term	Explanation
Partners	All partners of the SIENNA project are organisations – full or associate. ‘Full partners’ refers to any of the 11 beneficiaries of the project who receive funding for project activities. ¹ ‘Associate partners’ refers to the two non-crucial partners who do not receive funding for project activity.
Plain language	Communicating in a clear, concise and structured way, avoiding jargon or convoluted language (i.e., in plain writing or plain English).
Readability testing	Using algorithms developed to test the level of education/literacy required to comprehend text with specific attributes and/or structure (e.g., number of words in sentences, length of words).
Session	A website session is a group of interactions with a website during a certain amount of time. One session can include multiple page views and interactions.
Stakeholder	A relevant actor (persons, groups or organisations) who: (1) might be affected by the project; (2) have the potential to implement the project’s results and findings; (3) have a stated interest in the project fields; and, (4) have the knowledge and expertise to propose strategies and solutions in the fields of genomics, human enhancement and human machine interactions i.e., artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. (SIENNA D1.2 definition)
Unique page view	A unique page view aggregates page views generated by the same user in the same session. A unique page view represents the number of sessions during which that page was viewed one or more times.
Visual identity	Graphical identity and other visual components (such as colour scheme, fonts) used in SIENNA communications (i.e., web, printed materials, report and presentation templates).

Table 2: Glossary of terms

¹ SIENNA, Description of Action, Part B, p. 38.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The strategy to communicate about the SIENNA project and its results is developed in three steps. An initial phase (month 1-12, outlined in *D7.3 Communication and dissemination plan*), where we focus on raising awareness of the project and its results; a second phase (month 13-30, covering the initial steps outlined in this document) where we develop strategy for impact collaboration and interaction with key stakeholders; and a final phase (month 31-42) where work in the first two phases will help build a strategy for achieving impact. This report covers the first phase and part of the second phase, reporting on the first steps towards building strategy for impact collaboration with other projects and initiatives, the use of SIENNA channels, and metrics to evaluate the project's reach.

This document also addresses recommendations from the European Commission's Research Executive Agency review report for SIENNA covering the period from 01/10/2017 to 30/09/2018, asking for a more active social media approach to reach wider publics, and metrics awareness raising, for which we use outreach metrics as a proxy.

1.2 Objectives

This report describes communication and dissemination activities carried out between October 2017 and May 2019 (where applicable) and reports them in relation to the tentative list of Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) outlined in the *SIENNA Communication and dissemination plan (D7.3)*.

As SIENNA has moved to the second phase in the communications strategy, this document also outlines how communications strategy has evolved since submitting the initial communication and dissemination plan (D7.3). This includes social media strategy.

In addition, this report aims to outline the first steps taken to develop impact strategy for AI, which will serve as an example for how this can be done for the other technology domains in SIENNA. The report also describes next steps, planning, review and tracking of scientific publication (Task 7.4), and suggests measures to address challenges in relation to this.

1.3 Structure of the report

This report consists of six parts: 1) Introduction; 2) report on the first steps taken towards impact strategy and sustainability planning (as part of the second phase of developing communications strategy for SIENNA); 3) report on the scientific dissemination; 4) report on external communication activities; 5) report on internal communication activities; and 6) next steps.

1.4 Scope and limitations

This is an interim report on SIENNA communication and dissemination activities, outlining work carried out in several work packages, which have been tracked and coordinated by WP7.

At the time of writing this report, we are in the process of developing strategy for impact collaboration with actors outside the SIENNA project. Because of developments outside the SIENNA project, where attention is very much focused on developing ethical guidance for artificial intelligence, SIENNA communication activities have focused mainly on AI, in order to exploit opportunities. This means that

thinking for how to communicate in an impactful way for the other technology areas have not been developed to the same extent.

In terms of KPI's, data is not yet available for some of the measures outlined in in the communication and dissemination plan (D7.3), as the project recently started publishing results. This means that downloads, citations and Altmetric data are not (yet) meaningful to report, and have been excluded from this report.

2. Impact strategy and sustainability planning

To achieve impact, SIENNA needs to produce outputs that are relevant to stakeholders and that are timely, asked for, and/or gives input to their ongoing processes.

The SIENNA project will develop a number of exploitable outputs, including:

- Ethical **frameworks** for Human Genomics, Human Enhancement, AI & Robotics
- Ethical **guidelines** for researchers and innovators in industry and academia
- **Protocols and operational guidelines** for research ethics committees
- **Recommendations** for better legislation for law- and policy makers
- **Methodology** for ethical analysis for academic researchers, clinicians and start-up companies
- **Methodology** for legal analysis for policy makers, human rights organisations and legal scholars
- **Guidance** on how to develop codes and guidelines for professional organisations
- **Methodology** to reconcile views and interests of scientists and citizens for research funding organisations

In connection with impact strategy planning, the discussion on how to curate and sustain these outputs have been initiated and work will continue in collaboration between WP7 and WP6 to align sustainability and exploitation planning with dissemination and communication plans to design impact strategy.

The different outputs of the SIENNA project have different audiences, and different exploitation routes. In the second half of 2019, the consortium as a whole will initiate work to identify specific actors (individuals and organisations) who can support uptake and implementation. Following this process, WP7 to develop tools and tactics to engage with these actors. Activities will include presenting results at conferences, academic publication (DOI), editorial text, infographics & training, newsletters, media, social media, policy briefs and SIENNA workshops and other stakeholder interactions.

Dissemination and communication can help support impact by:

- making outputs **discoverable and findable** (using DOI + complementary strategy to generate publicity)
- making outputs **available** (using Open Access)

- making outputs **relevant** (by re-framing and re-packaging content for different stakeholders and audiences)
- making it **understandable** (by translating content to other languages, but also by adapting the communication for different audiences)

We are now in a phase where work to develop impact strategy has begun, which feeds into the exploitation and sustainability planning for SIENNA, requiring more active collaboration between WP7 and WP6.

Figure 1: Impact strategy and sustainability planning

2.1 Impact collaboration

There are a number of opportunities for SIENNA to collaborate with other research initiatives and expert groups. There are several initiatives on AI, which makes developing impact strategy for AI timely, and work to develop strategy in this area has begun. The model for impact collaboration that we are currently developing for AI will most likely be transferable (at least in part) to robotics, human genomics and human enhancement. The success depends on initiatives taken by leaders of WP2, 3 and 4 in identifying opportunities, and developing impact strategy together with WP7 (where input from WP2, 3, 4 and 5 will be integrated into communication and dissemination plans and concrete actions).

PANELFIT & SHERPA: The SIENNA project is collaborating with two Horizon 2020 (H2020) projects: PANELFIT and SHERPA. The collaboration works on two levels: the coordinators of the projects meet regularly to discuss how to build synergies and achieve common goals. In parallel, the communication and dissemination leads meet monthly to discuss joint activities, focusing on explaining the scope and overlaps of the projects, sharing networks and carrying out joint promotional activities.

Chairing of the communications team meetings is shared between the projects; SIENNA initiated the series of meetings and chaired the first two, followed by SHERPA (chaired meeting 4 and 5), and now the responsibility has moved to the PANELFIT team (chairing meeting 6 and 7). Activities (completed and planned) include:

- Joint Power Point (PPT) template (completed, developed by the SIENNA comms team)

- Graphical representation of scopes and overlaps between the projects (completed, developed by the SIENNA comms team).
- Webinar presenting the three projects together (completed on May 20, organised by SIENNA, video will be posted on YouTube).
- Editorial text about the projects, their scopes, overlaps and potential for synergies for publication in Orbit (<https://www.orbit-rri.org/>), with authors from all three projects (under development).
- Joint video (under development).
- SHERPA & SIENNA “Ethics by Design” track at the 4TU Ethics Biannual Conference on 7-8 November 2019 (call for abstracts published).
- Joint session at American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) conference on 13-16 February 2020 (proposed).
- SHERPA and SIENNA joint membership in International Organization for Standardization (ISO) working group (in progress).

Figure 2: Graphic representation of scopes and overlaps between SIENNA, SHERPA and PANELFIT

Human Brain Project: Steps have been taken to develop a joint webinar on AI with the FET Flagship Human Brain Project’s Ethics & Society sub-project in the second half of 2019. Discussions on writing

a joint editorial have also been initiated and the SIENNA communications team have agreed to collaborate with the sub-project's communications team.

Next steps: In the coming year, we identify similar opportunities for robotics, human genomics and human enhancement, and develop communication and dissemination to exploit those opportunities to maximise impact.

Figure 3: Draft impact strategy for Artificial Intelligence

3. Scientific dissemination

SIENNA is starting to produce results that will be made available in published public deliverable reports and peer-reviewed journals. SIENNA will ensure all peer-reviewed articles are made available using open access (as outlined in the Grant Agreement article 29.2), which outlines that peer-reviewed articles must be published using either the gold or green route, that open access is encouraged for book chapters (that are not peer-reviewed). The consortium have agreed to use Uppsala University’s Digital Scientific Archive (DiVA) repository for the green route, ensuring sustainable parallel publishing. This has some immediate advantages for the purposes of tracking publications, as outputs from DiVA can be displayed on the SIENNA website. Further, the DiVA database will show the number of downloads for parallel published papers, and also displays Altmetric data (tracking the number of times the doi-link to the publication has been shared in news items or social media posts). This connection will be implemented on the SIENNA website in Q3, 2019. As the number of publications grows, we will also be able to track citations, downloads (of parallel published papers in the DiVA portal) and Altmetric data (showing scores based on how many times the doi-link to a paper has been published in social media and news outlets).

Of the KPIs set for scientific dissemination, one of four KPI’s have already been met with good measure of success, as members of the SIENNA consortium have delivered over 30 presentations at third party events (indicated in green in Table 3).

Activity	KPI	May 2019
Scientific publications	5 publications submitted/accepted (by month 42)	2/5
Open access	Gold open access or green open access provided by end of journal embargo	1/5
Webinars	6 webinars held by month 42	1/6
Presentations at third-party events (conferences and workshops)	9 held by month 42	31/9

Table 3: KPI’s for scientific dissemination

3.1 Scientific publications

So far, three papers with SIENNA results have been published with SIENNA members as lead authors. Two English language papers by authors from Uppsala University from the Genomics work stream, and one in Mandarin by authors from the Dalian University of Technology from the AI work stream. Two additional papers acknowledging that part of the work was funded by SIENNA have been published with non-SIENNA lead authors (genomics). Two manuscripts have been sent to the consortium for Intellectual Property (IP) review (also on genomics). These are book chapters and as such will not be peer-reviewed or published open access. Work to plan publications is ongoing (led by Trilateral Research).

3.1.1 Published papers

- Slokenberga S & Howard HC, The right to science and human germline editing. Sweden, its external commitments and the ambiguous national responses under the Genetic Integrity Act, [Förvaltningsrättslig Tidskrift](#), 2019;2:199-222.
- Canellopoulou-Bottis, Maria, [The Greek Law on Genetics and Genomics - An Overview and Outlook for Future Perspectives](#), SSRN, available online December 4, 2018

Papers and books in other languages than English

- Wang Q, Cao Y, The Value of "Intentional Thinking" in the Era of Artificial Intelligence, Journal of Dalian University of Technology (Social Science Edition), 2019 ; 40(4):6-12 (July 2019), published in Mandarin.
- Wang Q, Brey P (eds). Theory and Practice of Responsible Innovation, Science Press (in Chinese)

Papers published in collaboration with others

- Vears DF, Niemiec E, Howard HC, Borry P, [How do consent forms for diagnostic high-throughput sequencing address unsolicited and secondary findings? A content analysis](#), Clinical Genetics, 2018;94(3-4): 21-329.
- Vears DF, Niemiec E, Howard HC, Borry P, [Analysis of VUS reporting, variant reinterpretation and recontact policies in clinical genomic sequencing consent forms](#), European Journal of Human Genetics, 2018;26:1743–1751.

3.1.2 Publications under SIENNA IP review

- Niemiec E et al., Genethics and Public Health, chapter in Applied Genomics and Public Health (Elsevier)
- Niemiec E et al., Consenting Patients to Genome Sequencing, chapter in Clinical Genome Sequencing: Psychological Considerations (Elsevier)

3.1.3 Planned publications

- Fernow J, de Miguel Beriain I, Brey P & Stahl B, Setting future ethical standards for ICT, Big Data, AI and robotics - the contribution of three European projects, editorial text for publication in Orbit.

3.2 Presentations (oral and posters)

SIENNA researchers have presented their work at a number of events (see full list in Annex 1).

Presentations	2017	2018	2019 (until June)	People reached	Audiences
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AI & Robotics	0	14	1	1233	Scientific Community, Industry, Policy Makers
Human Enhancement	0	1	3	310	Scientific Community, Civil Society, General Public
Human Genomics	1	3	4	1565	Scientific Community, Industry, Civil Society, General Public
About SIENNA	1	3	0	155	Scientific Community, General Public
Total	2	21	8	3259	

Table 4: SIENNA Presentation KPI's, number of people reached and audiences

3.3 Webinars

SIENNA uses webinars to engage with stakeholders, present results and manifest collaborations with other projects, and produce content for web and social media. So far, we have organised one webinar together with the PANELFIT and SHERPA projects. Presentations were captured on video, which will be published on the SIENNA [YouTube channel](#) in three separate clips: 1) the entire webinar, 2) the introductory slides presenting the three projects together, and 3) the presentation on SIENNA's work on Artificial Intelligence. This strategy will allow us to use the videos for different purposes, showing both what we do in relation to AI, who we collaborate with, and where the scopes and overlaps are. We also reinforce our collaboration with the PANELFIT and SHERPA communications teams by offering them mp4 clips of the presentation(s) to use in their own channels, both to promote their own projects, and the collaboration.

For Q3 and Q4 2019, we plan one webinar presenting the SIENNA project as a whole, and one webinar together with the Human Brain Project's Ethics and Society sub-project, on artificial intelligence. Later on, WP leads are also expected to present SIENNA's work on robotics, human genomics and human enhancement, facilitated by WP7.

Webinars fulfil a number of purposes: They facilitate scientific dissemination, but they can also be used as a marketing tool, and work as a means promote the project. In terms of KPI's, actual number of attendants is not the only relevant metric. The act of promoting the webinar gives attention to the topic the webinar addresses, shows that SIENNA is active in this particular field, promotes the project and drives traffic from the channel where the webinar is being promoted to other SIENNA channels (e.g., from Twitter to web).

Note: At the time of writing this report, the webinar videos had not been uploaded to YouTube, hence there are no metrics for number of views to report.

Title of webinar (including planned)	Date	Registered attendees	No of tweets	No of views
SIENNA/SHERPA/PANELFIT AI webinar	20/05/19	39	15	N/A
SIENNA project	Q3-4/19	-	-	-
SIENNA & HBP ethics & society	Q3-4/19	-	-	-
SIENNA & Human Genomics	TBD	-	-	-
SIENNA & Human Enhancement	TBD	-	-	-

SIENNA & Robotics	TBD	-	-	-
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Table 5: Webinars (including planned) and KPI's

4. Strategy for external communication

To ensure communications coming from the SIENNA project are relevant to stakeholders and other audiences, we have separated the domains in our communications. The website has four landing pages, one for the project as a whole (www.sienna-project.eu), one for human genomics (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/genomics/>), one for human enhancement (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/enhancement/>), and one for AI & robotics (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/robotics/>). The domain specific landing pages have mirrored structure, but tailored content. This will help ensure that visitors recognise the project, and find content that is *domain specific and relevant to them*. This strategy to separate communications is also mirrored in the stakeholder analysis and stakeholder contact list (developed in SIENNA T1.4) and then applied to the newsletters, sending three separate mailings, with mirrored structures, and content tailored to the technology domain. In social media, this tactic is applied by using domain-specific hashtags (Twitter) and developing domain specific content (YouTube).

First phase (month 1-12): In the first 12 months, the SIENNA project launched a number of channels to communicate with different audiences, with the aim to raise awareness of the project and its results.

- Web: www.seinna-project.eu
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/SiennaEthics/>
- YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSn_2EYn7tDgz7ZD3fcF_0w

Tools and tactics for these channels were developed, along with a visual identity for the SIENNA project, which is used in all SIENNA communications, ranging from templates for reports and presentations, web, and newsletters, to social media and videos produced for the project.

Second phase (month 13-30): We have now entered the second phase, building strategy for impact collaboration for the different technology domains. At this time, there are several AI related activities external to SIENNA, with two ongoing H2020-funded projects focusing on the same domain (SHERPA and PANELFIT), and opportunities to collaborate on AI with the FET Flagship Human Brain Project. In addition, SIENNA have given input to the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, and we are also planning to give input to an initiative from ISO to develop global standards for trustworthy AI (SC42 AI standards). We are also looking for opportunities for impact collaboration with other actors for Robotics, Human Enhancement and Human Genomics. Opportunities are more limited for these fields. However, work initiated to develop impact strategy for AI could still serve as a model for these fields. Work to identify opportunities for SIENNA to collaborate with other research initiatives and expert groups in these fields will continue in the second half of 2019. On a more general level, outputs from the SIENNA project also has potential to have impact on the Horizon Europe programme.

4.1 SIENNA website

The SIENNA website (url: www.sienna-project.eu) has been fully operational since 29 September 2017. Uppsala University manages the domain registration and hosts the website on its servers, using the InfoGlue content management system. The structure of the website, process for developing the website and rationale for using separate landing pages is described in *D7.2 Website launch*, along with the website’s role in SIENNA communications, measures for accessibility and availability, roles and responsibilities (including content ownership).

Structure changes: One anticipated structure change was implemented on the website in May 2019, adding a tab for publications in the top navigation, and publication pages on all technology area landing pages.

Figure 4: SIENNA website top navigation with new publications tab

Figure 5: Genomics landing page with publications page added in navigation. This structure is mirrored on pages for Enhancement and AI & Robotics.

4.1.2 Measuring website performance

From October 2017 to March 2019, the website had a total of 16,145 unique page views (UPVs) from 4,934 unique users. April and May 2019 have not been included in this report. The reason being partly

that we evaluate website performance over six-month periods, and that three separate e-mail newsletters were issued from 15 May-29 May, 2019, driving traffic towards the website, which cannot be evaluated in this report.

The website’s performance in the first six months will serve as a benchmark for performance for the rest of the project duration. From October 2017 to March 2019, 4,934 users visited the SIENNA website, with 1,153 in the first six months.

Figure 6: Number of Unique Page Views of the SIENNA website per month October 2017 to March 2019 (from Google Analytics)

As shown in figure 6, the base level number of website visitors is stable, leaning towards an increase. Peaks in activity can be linked to @SiennaEthics Tweets, especially about SIENNA events, or activities asking for input from experts and stakeholders.

Sources of website traffic: Most of the website traffic was generated from Google searches (7,655 unique page views), indicating that the Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) of the website works in the projects’ favour. For 6,150 UPVs, data on the source of the traffic is unavailable. This means that Google Analytics was unable to gather information on the user before it entered the site, or that users typed the URL for the website directly into their browsers.

Number of page views: Aside from Google searches and untraceable visitors, the website generating the most unique page views was Uppsala University’s website (841) and Twitter (594). See table below for the most significant contributions to UPVs.

Source	Oct 17 – Mar 18	Apr 18 – Sep 18	Oct 18 – Mar 19	Total number of unique page views generated Oct 17 – Mar 19
All	4 753	3 993	7 399	16 145 (100%)
Search engines	1 945	2 017	3 695	7 655 (47,41%)
Direct hits/no cookies available	1 883	1 230	3 037	6 150 (38,09%)
Uppsala university website	395	180	266	841 (5,33%)
Twitter	224	217	153	594 (3,69%)
Facebook	113	39	44	196 (1,21%)
4TU.Centre for Ethics and Technology website	55	50	2	107 (0,66%)
Trilateral Research Ltd. website	36	21	5	77 (0,05%)

Marcelo-de-araujo.blogspot.com.br	25	4	-	29 (0,02%)
Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ) website	17	14	12	43 (0,03%)
ENERI website	-	-	4	4 (0,02%)
PANELFIT website	-	-	1	1 (0,01%)

Table 5: KPI: Sources that generated most unique page views for the SIENNA website (data from Google Analytics)

From the metrics in Table 5, it is clear that the efforts made at the beginning of the project to communicate its launch paid-off in the first 6 months with much traffic being driven from SIENNA partner and consortium member websites. The search engine metrics show that people are still interested in checking up on SIENNA, even when there is less traffic driven from partner and consortium member websites.

Sessions and users: Google Analytics records each website visit as a “session” and each unique visitor as a “user”. Every time a user visits only one page before leaving, this adds to the overall bounce rate. Sessions with the highest bounce rate are those where the landing page is a news item or an infographic, where the user has found what they are looking for immediately and then leave the SIENNA website. A bounce rate of around 55% is considered average. As the numbers in Table 6 show, the SIENNA website has a poor performance in terms of bounce rates. This is not surprising as social media metrics (see section 4.2) and web metrics together indicate that we often drive traffic from Twitter to news items and infographics that we post on Twitter. Measures to decrease bounce rates includes adding links to other parts of the SIENNA website in news items, and cross-link between pages to enable link-clicks for continued browsing. However, with the current Twitter strategy, we are unlikely to see significant decreases in bounce rates. In Q3 and Q4 2019, additional efforts will be made to see how website structure and content could develop to decrease the bounce rate.

SIENNA website	Oct 17 – Mar 18	Apr 18 – Sept 18	Oct 18 – Mar 19	Total
Sessions	1 959	2 072	3 602	7 633
Users	1 153	1 437	2 473	4 394
Sessions per user	1,7	1,44	1,46	1,55
Bounce rate	50,64%	61,39%	59,66%	57,81%
Average session duration (in minutes)	02:59	01:52	02:12	02:19
Pages per session	3,05	2,38	2,5	2,61

Table 7: KPI: Google Analytics metrics for website user behaviour

The average SIENNA website visitor stays on the page for 2 minutes and 19 seconds and looks at 2.61 pages. For longer texts and infographics, visitors for an average of 5 minutes, whereas they tend to click away from the home page faster.

As shown in Figure 7, there are various points of entry to the SIENNA website. Most common is for a user to enter through the start page (www.sienna-project.eu).

Figure 7: How SIENNA website users navigate the website.

The start page is by far the most visited, and this is where most users enter the SIENNA website (53,98%). From there, they primarily move on to learn more about SIENNA, SIENNA partners and people in SIENNA. The same thing goes for users who start at a news item on the SIENNA website, they then move on to read more news followed by About SIENNA, partners, people in SIENNA and finally the technology area-specific landing pages. Learning from this, the next steps in developing content for web is to add information about the people involved in different tasks to the technology-specific parts of the SIENNA web.

From the Google Analytics data, it is clear that news items and infographics do well in terms of keeping users on the website, and that what visitors are most interested in learning more about is the project itself, the partners and the people working in the project.

4.2 SIENNA social media strategy

In the initial phase of the project, SIENNA's social media presence focused on identifying stakeholders on social media and listening to social media conversation to see where SIENNA content fit. SIENNA established a Twitter account (@SiennaEthics) which at the time of writing (19 June 2019) has 417 followers (increased from 355 followers on 3 June 2019). Twitter users visit the platform to find news. When SIENNA results are ready to share, the social media presence will expand, and most likely include a LinkedIn page for the project, a consortium members have already shared information about the project on their own LinkedIn pages, and their presence there can help us build an audience. We will also consider strategy for ResearchGate.

4.2.1 Social media metrics

Algorithms push content that will keep users on their social media platform as long as possible. SIENNA uses various social media metrics to evaluate SIENNA's presence on social media and to learn what content our audience and the algorithm prefers.

Followers, retweets and likes are publicly available, but can only tell us so much about social media success rates. To get the full picture, we gather information about **reach**, **clicks** and **engagement rate** using our social media platforms' own analytic tools (Twitter Analytics, YouTube Analytics and, in the future, LinkedIn Page Analytics). When tracking the reach of our social media content, we can find out how big our audience is, i.e., how many people actually see our content (e.g., a tweet). This allows us to find out how far beyond our followers each post reaches, how big our organic audience actually is.

Beyond organic reach, finding out how many people actually click our links, watch our videos or expand our images can tell us if SIENNA content encourages the audience to learn more about the project. The Click and Reach metrics give us the Engagement rate. The engagement rate (Clicks divided by Reach) shows the percentage of the organic reach audience who chose to click the post to engage with SIENNA.

Figure 8: How clicks (engagements) divided by organic reach (impressions) give the engagement rate in Twitter Analytics.

Community engagement results in many interactions. Tweets where SIENNA interacts with consortium members are the tweets with the highest engagement rates. The audience responds well to displays of interest from others. Live-tweets from events, such as project workshops, give the audience an opportunity to follow SIENNA behind the scenes. These tweets also have a higher engagement rate than others. So do tweets that link to long-form news items on the SIENNA website, and include photos, screenshots or other images.

Live-tweets from project workshops has become a pillar of growing SIENNA’s Twitter audience. For example, the Twitter campaigns run from the latest project workshops (13-15 June in Uppsala and Gothenburg, Sweden) resulted in 50 new followers.

TWITTER STATS SUMMARY / USER STATISTICS FOR SIENNAETHICS (JUN 6TH, 2019 - JUN 20TH, 2019)							
DATE		FOLLOWERS		FOLLOWING		TWEETS	
2019-06-06	Thu	+1	358	+2	404	+2	370
2019-06-07	Fri	–	358	–	404	+2	372
2019-06-08	Sat	+2	360	–	404	+1	373
2019-06-09	Sun	–	360	+1	405	–	373
2019-06-10	Mon	+1	361	–	405	+1	374
2019-06-11	Tue	–	361	+1	406	+1	375
2019-06-12	Wed	–	361	–	406	+1	376
2019-06-13	Thu	+11	372	+18	424	+13	389
2019-06-14	Fri	+39	411	+6	430	+66	455
2019-06-15	Sat	+2	413	–	430	+1	456
2019-06-16	Sun	+2	415	–	430	–	456
2019-06-17	Mon	–	415	+2	432	+2	458
2019-06-18	Tue	+1	416	–	432	+1	459
2019-06-19	Wed	+1	417	🔴 LIVE	–	–	459
Daily Averages		+3		+1		+3	
Last 30 Days		+79		+37		+104	

Figure 9: SIENNA follower count from SocialBlade (<https://socialblade.com/twitter/user/siennaethics>)

We track the effectiveness of Twitter campaigns using SocialBlade. It is a service that once an account is registered collects and displays public metrics from social media accounts (i.e. followers, following and number of tweets). Data from SocialBlade shows that live-tweeting from project events does in fact lead to an increase in followers. Especially when workshop participants are also tweeting during the workshops. In order to make this possible, SIENNA ensures we follow workshop participants on Twitter before the workshop. We also create unique hashtags where people can follow the workshop discussions and tag the event (see section 4.2.2 Twitter hashtag strategy).

@SiennaEthics	Nov 2017 – Apr 2019	May 2018 – Oct 2018	Nov 2018 – Apr 2019	Total Twitter engagements
No of tweets	14	20	82	116
Reach	24 274	36 991	107 029	168 294
Clicks	425	331	1 153	1 909
Retweets	39	59	170	268
Likes	53	86	349	488
User profile clicks	50	15	147	212
URL clicks	70	68	139	277
Hashtag clicks	42	6	41	89
Detail expands	142	54	138	334
Media views	29	66	82	484
Media engagements	29	40	164	233
Replies	0	2	4	6
Engagement rate	1,75%	0,89%	1,16%	1,13%

Table 8: KPI: @SiennaEthics Twitter engagements November 2017 – April 2019

There are different ways the Twitter audience can interact with a tweet. SIENNA’s most retweeted content is that which features results from the project or from project partners, and invitations to participate in SIENNA research (i.e., links to publications, surveys or infographics). The same goes for obtaining likes from our Twitter audience, although videos are also liked fairly often. For user profile clicks, generated when audience members click to visit SIENNA’s Twitter feed, what is most efficient is mentioning consortium members using their full name or Twitter handle. Of course, it helps if the tweet links to something of interest to its audience, if it is a live-tweet from an event or an invitation to contribute to SIENNA. For our audience to click our links, Twitter metrics (as listed in Annex 1) show the value of offering links to content where Twitter users can read longer texts, so called “long-form” content, whether it be research results from partners or interviews with SIENNA consortium members.

Sharing videos, infographics and live-tweets from events also generates more URL clicks from our audience. Hashtag clicks are less frequent, however the value of using popular hashtags (such as #AutonomousCars in March 2018, or an event hashtag like #SiennaEthicsUU18) should not be underestimated. When a Twitter user expands the tweet, the metric “detail expand” indicates that the audience was interested in learning more about the contents of a tweet. Detail expands are more frequent for tweets that include either a photo, or a screenshot. The “media views” metric indicates that Twitter users have viewed an image or video embedded in the tweet. Metrics show that posting photos and in-stream video generates engagement, as does the use of screenshots of content that the

tweet links to (long-form content). The media engagement metric indicates that the audience clicks on the image or video. This is more frequent for images that include a lot of information, such as screenshots teasing long-form content.

Figure 10: Examples of @SiennaEthics Tweets with high engagement rates

The tweets with the most impressions (i.e. tweets with a large *organic reach*), are tweets encouraging the audience to participate in SIENNA research, that mention researchers by name and that share links to long-form content.

When comparing SIENNA’s Twitter statistics from the first six months with the second, there is a drop in engagement rate. Since then, it has recovered somewhat. In first quarter of 2019, the audience growth is apparent. With a six-fold increase in impressions, SIENNA’s organic reach has grown significantly, so has the number of individual engagements. The change in engagement rate varies from tweet to tweet, depending on the type of content and/or campaign. The overall trend points towards increasing engagement rates as we have more content to share and our audience builds.

To monitor the tone in interactions between audience members and SIENNA, we use social media listening and **sentiment analysis** to monitor perception of the SIENNA project. This shows that most social media users mentioning SIENNA use a **neutral to positive sentiment**. There are also some examples of *very positive* feedback on Twitter.

Figure 11: Example of positive sentiment expressed about SIENNA on Twitter

Comparing and contrasting with “competitors” is another tool to measure social media success rate. SIENNA should be benchmarked against other H2020 projects in the Ethical Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) of AI and Robotics, Human Enhancement and Human Genomics fields, along with other H2020 projects that started October 2017. In comparison to the SHERPA and PANELFIT projects (covering the ethical, legal and human rights aspects of big data and data sharing), SIENNA is doing well on Twitter, with more activity (tweets) and a higher number of followers. Part of this difference is because SHERPA and PANELFIT are ‘younger’ than SIENNA. When compared to other projects that started in October 2017, SIENNA is also doing well, with only 4 of 19 other projects with dedicated Twitter accounts having more followers (i.e., FLEXCoop, ReUseHeat, Stardust, and TRAIN-EV).

Project name (and Twitter handle)	Tweets	Following	Followers
SIENNA (@SiennaEthics)	459	432	417
SHERPA (@project-sherpa)	101	90	222
PANELFIT (@panelfit)	20	40	86
EASITrain (@EasiTrain)	183	155	54
PhD4GlucoDrug (@PhD4GlycoDrug)	5	-	30
Analytics4Biologics (@Analytics4Bio)	9	5	6
ATHOR (@etnathor)	220	114	110
RESOLVD (@REOLVD_EU)	447	74	159
FLEXCoop (@FLEXCoop_H2020)	545	312	353
mcBEEs (@itn_mcBEEs)	13	20	14
ReUseHeat Project (@ReUseHeat)	489	262	450
Nanostencil (@Nanostencil_EU)	3	6	5
CHE Project (@che_project)	112	179	169
Stardust (@Stardust2020)	600	161	435
HOLISDER project (@HolisderProject)	159	482	262
ConFlex consortium (@ConFlex2017)	47	16	25
Mat4Rail (@Mat4Rail)	36	162	93
H2020-MEMO2 (@H2020_MEMO2)	70	66	49
Spine (@Spine_Project)	56	90	41
TRAIN-EV (@train_ev)	122	199	396

Table 9: KPI: SIENNA benchmarked against Public Twitter metrics of other H2020 projects (20 June 2019)

Out of the five most followed projects, SIENNA is the most active. Both FLEXCoop and ReUseHeat connect to a social cause (global warming), which might make it easier for them to recruit followers. Stardust and TRAIN-EV are more niche, meaning they do not share SIENNA's challenge of keeping stakeholders in three technology areas interested at the same time. The chart entirely excludes projects using partner organisations' accounts for their project communications, as they have different audiences.

The SIENNA project aims to reach a number of different publics. Mostly stakeholder audiences (ranging from individuals working in the different technology areas and/or doing ELSI research, to members of the "general" public, i.e. individual who are interested in science, technology, human rights, ethics, law, research policy, philosophy, and/or its impacts for society). Measuring this kind of outreach is difficult, as all of our followers are members of one or more overlapping publics. Twitter offers some metrics to help assess whether we indeed reach a sample of the audiences we aim for. According to Twitter analytics, 61% of SIENNA's followers are female, and 39% are male. Their top interest is science news, followed by dogs and the weather. The latter indicates that our followers are not only using Twitter in a professional capacity. Audience interests also include tech news, education, politics and commentary, which suggests that we in fact *do* reach the publics we are aiming for, and by implication (politics and commentary) that they are indeed interested in the ethical, legal and societal issues connected to new and emerging technologies.

To capitalise on our audience's interests, part of our social media strategy consists of creating buy-in from stakeholders by connecting the SIENNA project to recent events and sharing news from partners related to genomics, enhancement, AI and robotics. Our audience consists mostly of project stakeholders, meaning such news can be calls for abstracts, live tweets from events and recent publications from partner organisations. SIENNA's Twitter audience is also interested in education, which is why we are also breaking down SIENNA results into useful infographics and video content. To spread the word about SIENNA, and connect to stakeholders, we also make sure to be present in hashtag feeds relating to the ELSI of new and emerging technologies.

4.2.2 Twitter hashtag strategy

All content shared on SIENNA social media is not relevant to all stakeholders. For stakeholders to be able to navigate to find SIENNA tweets on their technology area of interest, three separate hashtags have been created alongside the project joint hashtag #SiennaEthics:

- #SiennaEnhancement
- #SiennaGenomics
- #SiennaRoboticsAI

Further, SIENNA uses hashtags to enable conversation about project workshops. So far, the following hashtags have been used for our workshops:

- #SiennaEthicsUU18 (Uppsala University workshops 4-5 April 2018)
- #SiennaLegalAspects (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights workshop, 8-9 November 2018)
- #FutureImpactsAI (Trilateral Research Ltd. workshop, 15-16 January 2019)
- #FutureImpactsRobotics (Trilateral Research Ltd. workshop, 15-16 January 2019)
- #FutureImpactsEnhancement (Trilateral Research Ltd. workshop, 16-17 January 2019)
- #FutureImpactsGenomics (Trilateral Research Ltd. workshop, 18 January 2019)
- #SiennaEthics (Ionian University workshop, 9-11 April 2019)
- #EthicsofRobotics & EthicsofAI (Uppsala University workshop, 13-14 June 2019)
- #EthicsofEnhancement (Uppsala University workshop, 13-14 June 2019)
- #EthicsofGenomics & ESHG19 (Uppsala University workshop in Gothenburg 14-15 June 2019, in connection with the European Society of Human Genetics meeting)

The Tweets from SIENNA events have been combined into Twitter Moments that enable our audience to revisit these events. At the time of writing, Twitter is updating its' use of moments and launching an explore tab. This makes it harder for Twitter users in Europe to access Twitter Moment, at least for the time-being.

Aside from SIENNA's own hashtags, community hashtags are continuously evaluated to ensure SIENNA content is visible in channels read by SIENNA stakeholders. For AI & robotics, we use the more general #AI, #robotics #MachineLearning, #BigData and other content relevant tags. As the AI developments are currently being widely covered by media and new policy and regulations is being developed *right now*, hashtags for this technology area are easier to identify, and more widely used, than those that cover other technology areas in SIENNA. Some examples of ELSI hashtags identified for AI are #ResponsibleAI, #Alethics, #HumanAI and #AIforGood, connecting us to the current flow of Twitter content. For Human Enhancement, we use a more general hashtag strategy, including #Enhancement, #ELSI and relevant hashtags for the different enhancement technologies (which sometimes correlates with AI and Genomics hashtags). For genomics, we similarly use #genetics, #genomics coupled with #ELSI, together with technology relevant hashtags (e.g. #NGS, #GeneEditing), and event relevant hashtags (e.g. #ESHG19).

4.3 Using video to communicate

The SIENNA strategy for video communication includes: 1) translating; 2) tailoring; 3) re-framing; and 4) educating. By creating video that can be adapted and re-used, such as translating video to partner's own languages, we make sure the content is tailored to partners' specific communication needs and can help support a more "local" impact. In order to extend our reach to lay publics, SIENNA project videos aim to use plain language.

We also need SIENNA videos to be useful in other channels. We use the Biteable video tool (<https://biteable.com/>), which allows for creation and adaptation of videos for various audiences in various languages. It allows us to generate 1080p MP4-files which can be played offline and used by consortium members and partners at SIENNA and third-party events. For long form content, such as recorded webinars, we use the Adobe Premiere Pro to edit video and audio before publishing to the SIENNA YouTube channel. YouTube allows users to upload high-resolution videos up to 24 hours long,

which means it is possible to upload both social media length videos and more extensive content such as recorded webinars.

SIENNA’s YouTube channel is primarily a repository to make project videos shareable (on social media) and embeddable (on project’s own and other websites). This means that the purpose of the SIENNA YouTube channel is not to build a following or engage socially. Therefore, rather than tracking subscribers (total 18), we are tracking **watch time** as a KPI.

The SIENNA YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSn_2EYn7tDgz7ZD3fcF_0w) launched 11 November 2017 and the SIENNA project video generated 177 views in the first month. With the addition of new, translated versions in July 2018 generated some more views and with the addition of technology area specific videos in September and November 2018 and January 2019, the base level for watch time per month has increased continuously.

Figure 12: Total watch time for SIENNA YouTube videos, embedded and native, November 2017 to April 2019

In the first six months of 2018, 315 minutes worth of SIENNA YouTube content was watched. Between May 2018 and October the same year, viewers spent 376 minutes watching SIENNA videos. In total, our YouTube audience spent 1205 minutes watching SIENNA YouTube videos (November 2017 through April 2019). Still, these figures do not include videos uploaded in-stream as native content on Twitter (e.g.: <https://twitter.com/SiennaEthics/status/1098578549085257730>). The two videos shared on Twitter this way have 213 views combined.

Video	Nov 17 – Apr 18	May 18 – Oct 18	Nov 18 – Apr 19	Total
Views	376	386	595	1 138
Watch time	315	376	717	1 205
Impressions	897	1 785	3 748	6 430

Table 10: KPI’s for SIENNA video (examples)

Views, watch time and impressions have increased since the launch of SIENNA’s YouTube channel. The main traffic source for the SIENNA YouTube channel is the SIENNA project website. Impressions are only generated when thumbnails are displayed to viewers on YouTube.

Source	Views	Watch time (in minutes)
sienna-project.eu	43	62
YouTube	32	42
Twitter	43	38
Facebook	48	35
Google Search	30	29
rri-tools.eu	8	10
Gmail	12	9
WhatsApp	5	8
ufrj.br	4	3

Table 11: Most significant traffic sources for the SIENNA YouTube channel (1 Nov 2017-April 2019)

Videos on YouTube can be shared via Facebook and Twitter, e-mail or chat, and they appear in Google searches. Table 10 confirms that we are more likely to reach stakeholders with SIENNA video content if those videos are available where that stakeholders already frequent, such as the SIENNA project website, the RRI Tools website and Federal University of Rio de Janeiro’s website and social networking sites.

4.4 Talking to stakeholders: SIENNA workshops

The SIENNA project has organised a number of stakeholder workshops and two public events (more information about events available at <http://www.sienna-project.eu/workshops>). The second phase of the communications strategy planning is dependent on input from stakeholders and experts to ensure key messages fit the audience. This is also where most of SIENNA interactions with stakeholders occurs (see figure 12). For this reason, SIENNA webinars and workshops provide input not only to the outputs coming from the project, but also helps shape the way we talk about them.

Figure 13: Phases in SIENNA communications strategy in relation to project workshops & conferences

4.4.1 Stakeholder workshops

- The first SIENNA stakeholder workshop was hosted by Uppsala University, Sweden on 4-5 April 2018, discussing fundamental aspects of the project.
- The second stakeholder workshop covering the legal aspects was hosted by the Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights in Poland on 8-9 November 2018.
- The third, fourth and fifth stakeholder workshop(s) on future impacts and ethical challenges for AI & Robotics, Human Enhancement and Genomics respectively was hosted by Trilateral Research Ltd in London, United Kingdom on 15-18 January 2019.

- The sixth stakeholder workshop on ethical analysis was hosted by the Ionian University in Athens on 9-10 April 2019.
- The seventh and eighth stakeholder workshop(s) on ethical challenges for AI & Robotics and Human Enhancement were hosted by Uppsala University in Uppsala on 13-14 June 2019.
- The ninth workshop on ethical challenges for Human Genomics was hosted by Uppsala University in Gothenburg on 14-15 June 2019 in connection with the European Society of Human Genetics meeting (15-18 June 2019).

4.5 Public events

To generate attention for the SIENNA project, two public events have been organised in connection with SIENNA workshops: One in connection with the Fundamentals workshop in Uppsala, one in connection with the Legal Aspects workshop in Warsaw.

On 4 April 2018, SIENNA organised an open session together with Uppsala University's Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), inviting staff from the Biomedical Centre campus and the Science for Life Laboratory to an afterwork, where SIENNA's Saskia Nagel gave a public lecture entitled "Human enhancement: From cradle to grave – promises & challenges" (more information: <http://www.sienna-project.eu/afterwork/>).

On 7 November 2018, Professor Roger Brownsword gave an open lecture at Warsaw University on "the technological disruption of law: Law Disrupted, Law Re-Imagined, Law Re-Invented". The event was organised in collaboration with the Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (more information: <http://sienna-project.eu/news/news-item/?tarContentId=753038>).

4.5 Issuing newsletters

Regular newsletters will be issued by the SIENNA project using the contact lists of the project. To ensure these communications are helpful and relevant to stakeholders, the consortium agreed to delay the first communication from the project until we had public results to share. The consortium also agreed to issue separate communications to stakeholders in human genomics, human enhancement, AI & robotics. In essence, developing three separate newsletters, for three audiences, that overlap to some extent (stakeholders in human genomics might overlap with human enhancement, which in turn might have overlaps with stakeholders in AI and robotics). For this reason, these communications are spaced one week apart, not to over-burden recipients.

The decision to wait until SIENNA results were made public resulted in delay from the timing proposed in the DoA. This strategy and the rationale behind it was reported in the review meeting at the European Commission on 11 January 2019. The plan was to issue our first newsletters after the Commission had approved the deliverable reports. However, due to delays in that process, SIENNA issue the newsletters in May 2019, with the aim to offer stakeholders a chance to connect with the SIENNA project in different ways, ranging from only receiving newsletters, through invitations to workshops, input through surveys, consultations or interviews, to invitations to review our deliverable reports.

The first newsletter issued was for AI & robotics with the aim to promote the PANELFIT/SHERPA/SIENNA webinar (see section 4.1), This was followed by the human genomics

newsletter, with the aim to promote a publication on the right to science and human germline editing (Sweden, its external commitments and the ambiguous national responses under the Genetic Integrity Act), which was published in May. The last newsletter to be issued was on Human Enhancement, as there were no external circumstances that affected the decision on timing.

The newsletters are issued using the Mailchimp software, which allows for us to separate the audiences, allowing subscribers to opt in and/or out of one or more technology domains using the same interface. We use one subscription form for all technology areas (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/newsletter/>), and one form to connect with the project (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/connect/>), which also allows for newsletter subscription. A data protection notice is also provided in the newsletter footer.

The Mailchimp software also offers KPI metrics in the form of open rates, click rate, the number of bounces, and unsubscribes. In addition, we can measure outreach by looking at the number of people who submit the form to connect with the project the week after sending out the newsletter.

The SIENNA Mailchimp list (managed by Uppsala University) has a total of 859 subscribers (29 May 2019), with 318 subscribers for Human Enhancement, 321 for Human Genomics, and 454 subscribers for AI & Robotics), with some overlaps between the audiences. The performance of the first issues will serve as benchmark for future issues. From 15 May to 4 June 2019, 76 stakeholders signed up to Connect with SIENNA through the project website.

Newsletter issue	Date	Subscribers	Bounces	Opens	Clicks
AI & Robotics	15/05/19	454	23	43,9%	11,6%
Human Genomics	21/05/19	321	23	40,3%	7,4%
Human Enhancement	28/05/19	318	27	44,3%	13,1%

Table 12: KPI's for SIENNA newsletters (figures from 3 June 2019)

4.6 Publicity

The SIENNA project issued a press release in English and Dutch (reported in D7.1) to launch the project. The project has received quite a bit off media attention, both in relation to the press-release, and after, in English, Chinese, Dutch, German, Greek, Portuguese, Spanish, and Swedish language media. Including interviews, translated press-release content, editorial text, blog posts, news items on web and in newsletters, and social media mentions.

English

- [The underdog in the AI ethical and legal debate: human autonomy](#), Ethics Dialogues, 12 June 2019
- [Harnessing existing human rights jurisprudence to guide AI](#), Digital Freedom Fund, 8 April 2019
- [Are AI, big data and robotics changing life for the better or for the worse?](#), Trilateral Research News, 7 Nov 2018
- [Algorithms and Justice](#), medium.com, 9 Jul 2018
- [When AI, big data, ethics and human rights converge](#), Cordis, 22 Jun 2018

- [When AI, big data, ethics and human rights converge](#), Global Banking and Finance Review, 9 June 2018
- [When AI, big data, ethics and human rights converge](#), Project Sherpa, 30 May 2018
- [What impact will new technologies have on our lives? Job losses or new opportunities?](#) Trilateral Research News, 5 February 2018
- [AI ethics, foresight and ethics by design: Digital Ethics Summit](#), Trilateral Research News, 16 Jan 2018
- [Ethics, human rights and responsible innovation — THE ETHICS BLOG](#), Baraza Foundation, Charter for International Human Rights Accountability, 24 November 2017
- [Cyborgs urge humans to see the light at Leiden’s Brave New World conference](#), DutchNews.nl, 3 November 2017
- [Ethics, human rights and responsible innovation](#), Ethics Blog, 31 October 2017
- [Trilateral to support the co-ordination of multi-million Euro project on ethics and human rights impact of new technologies](#), web news from Trilateral Research, 19 October 2017
- [SIENNA: Preparing the ground for responsible innovation](#), web news from Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), Uppsala University, 19 October 2017
- [Research on ethical and legal aspects of new technologies](#), web news from the University of Twente, 24 April 2017

Chinese

- [我校人文学部科技伦理团队参加欧盟科技伦理合作项目启动会议](#), News from the Dalian University of Technology, 30 October 2017

Dutch

- [‘Zoals mensen kunnen discrimineren, kan kunstmatige intelligentie dat ook’](#), Innovatie Estafette, 16 April 2019
- [Ethische basis voor verantwoorde innovatie](#), link Magazine, 24 October 2017
- [Ethische basis voor verantwoorde innovatie](#), Press-release from the University of Twente, 24 October 2017
- [Dit zijn de 3 ethische grenzen aan technologie, vindt UT-professor](#), Tubantia 13 May 2017
- [UT buigt zich over ethiek en technologie](#), Computable, 5 May 2017
- [Groot Europees onderzoek naar regels voor nieuwe technologieën](#), NPO Radio 1, 2 May 2017
- [Onderzoek naar ethische en juridische aspecten van nieuwe technologie](#), Press-release from the University of Twente, 28 April 2017

German

- [Human Enhancement: Technische Optimierung von der Wiege bis zur Bahre](#), SuchtMagazin, January 2018

Greek

- [Δεύτερη συνάντηση της Γενικής Συνέλευσης του έργου SIENNA Horizon 2020](#), Ionian University web news, 11 Nov 2018
- [Έργο SIENNA](#), IHRC, 29 October 2018
- [SIENNA: Ετοιμάζοντας το έδαφος για υπεύθυνη καινοτομία](#), Ionian University web news, 20 October 2018
- [Ερευνητικό Έργο Sienna με τη συμμετοχή του Ιονίου πανεπιστημίου: Όταν η τεχνολογία συναντά την ηθική!](#), CNN Greece, 20 Oct 2018

Portugese

- [O avanço tecnológico e os desafios éticos](#), feature article in Rio Pesquisa - no 41 - Ano XI, pp 14-18 (quarterly magazine on science and technology published by FAPERJ), December 2017
- [UFRJ recebeu 38 mil euros para participação em projeto da União Europeia](#), web news from the Program for Bioethics, Applied Ethics and Public Health, UFRJ, Brazil, 21 November 2017

Spanish

- [Investigadores evaluarán el impacto de las nuevas tecnologías en los derechos humanos](#), 20 minutos, 26 October 2017
- [Un equipo de investigación internacional evaluará el impacto de las nuevas tecnologías en los derechos humanos](#), Press release from the University of Granada, published in UGR divulga, Canal UGR, 26 October 2017

Swedish

- [Teknik, etik och mänskliga rättigheter](#), Etikbloggen, 31 October 2017
- [SIENNA-projektet lägger grunden för ansvarsfull teknikanvändning](#), News from the Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), Uppsala University, 19 October 2017

5. Internal communication

The SIENNA project uses the University of Twente's (UT) SharePoint server to store and share key documents. The consortium meets regularly, both in Project Management Committee (PMC) meetings (frequency between once a month and once every two months), and in different work-package meetings (frequency as needed). Internal communications are facilitated by the management team at UT, the SIENNA coordinator, deputy coordinator and work package leaders.

Minutes and key documents for all WP and management activities are stored on SharePoint. Access to the SharePoint server is managed by UT. However, as some partners have difficulties accessing SharePoint, key documents like minutes from the PMC meetings are also circulated via e-mail.

The management team uses Skype to conduct regular PMC meetings, which is also the preferred tool by many WP leads, while others use different meeting software solutions such as GoToMeeting and Zoom based on their institutional policies.

6. Next steps

In preparation for exploitation and sustainability planning (carried out in WP6), the SIENNA consortium will identify the users of the frameworks, codes, recommendations, methodologies and guidance. This work will provide input to the continued development of impact strategy for the SIENNA project and allow us to design purposeful communication and dissemination activities, ensuring that WP7 supports impact in the best possible way.

Work to develop collaborations with the Human Brain Project's Ethics and Society sub-project will continue, aiming to develop a webinar and potentially a joint editorial publication in the second half of 2019. The ongoing collaboration with PANELFIT and SHERPA will continue, and the communications teams will explore the possibilities for other joint activities, and plan for result dissemination to achieve impact in the AI stakeholder community together.

In the second half of 2019, WP6, WP7 and WP8 will initiate discussions on impact, exploitation and sustainability planning. WP2, 3 and 4 leaders will be asked to drive the process to identify key stakeholders and partners for impact collaboration in order to identify key messages and opportunities for SIENNA to achieve impact in all technology domains.

WP7 will continue to evaluate the key performance indicator metrics presented in this report in relation to what the consortium wishes to achieve, to ensure communication activities are purposeful and helpful. WP7 will continue to tailor the dissemination and communication strategy, developing tools and tactics for reaching more specific stakeholder audiences to achieve the objectives of uptake and implementation. This will include presenting results at conferences, academic publication (DOI), editorial text, infographics & training, newsletters, media, social media, policy briefs and SIENNA workshops and other stakeholder interactions.

Learning from KPI metrics, SIENNA will develop web content describing the roles of different people in the project for the technology-specific parts of the SIENNA website.

We will continue planning and discussions with SIENNA partners to progress further scientific dissemination activities to maximise the impact and exploitation of the project's findings and output.

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Note about Annex 1: Dissemination and communication activities: This annex consists of activity tracking and has been submitted under separate cover (excel document).